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A Game Theoretical Model Of Cooperative Advertising And Pricing Policy In A Manufacturer-Distributor-Retailer Channel

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ABSTRACT

Series of recent works on cooperative advertising had investigated the Manufacture-Distributor-Retailer relationship at different level but non actually considered a scenario where the distributor is directly involved in advertising and also simultaneously involved in provision of subsidy to the retailer. This work used Stackelberg game theory to model the effect of advertising and subsidy on the players' payoffs in supply channel. The work used backward induction to obtain the advertising efforts, subsidy rates and players pricing. The player's price, the distributor advertising effort, the distributor's subsidy rate, the retailer advertising effort and the manufacturer's subsidy rate were obtained and observed that when the distributor is incorporated into a supply chain as an integral part of the relationship, the distributor bears part of the advertising burden and consequentially increases the profit of the entire system. The distributor and manufacturer over-subsidised the retailer's advertising effort, which should not have been so because the profit of the retailer will become unbounded and the distributor may put out of business because of its simultaneous involvement in both direct and indirect advertising that will definitely take a chunk of its fund. Hence, optimum strategy ought to be adopted by all member in terms pricing, advertising effort and subsidy availment to ensure all member remain in business and profit is optimized.

Keywords: Cooperative advertising, Subsidised rate, Stackelberg game, Advertising effort

INTRODUCTION

Cooperative advertising is a key tool which plays a fundamental role in promoting sales in a three-member channel. This work focuses on cooperative advertising and its pricing policy in a manufacturer, distributor and retailer relationship (supply chain). The manufacturer is the Stackelberg leader while the distributor and the retailer are the first follower and second follower respectively. This paper seeks to unravel the effect of cooperative advertising and pricing policy on a three-member channel using game theory and the impact of the distributor in a three channel. The game model will be developed on the setting that both the retailer and the distributor are directly involved in advertising the product of the manufacturer, while there is also the cooperative involvement of the manufacturer and distributor through subsidy availment for the retailer's advertising effort. This scenario is applicable where there is need for large state-wise awareness of a manufacturer's product where the distributor is domiciled, which can be directly handled by the distributor and a need to target the local consumers which will be handled by the retailer. The distributor can also participate in pulling funds together with the manufacturer to support the

retailer large scale advertisement effort at the grassroots level since the retailer is closer to the final consumer. The cost of reaching larger scale consumers may be too burdensome for the retailer if not supported, hence the distributor may decide to divide its advertising budget into two, some for its state-wise directly advertisement and the other portion for its support towards the retailer's advertising effort known as subsidy. This advertising cost could be in form of discount or price reduction proportional to a portion of what is received from the manufacturer as a price margin. Although in this scenario, the distributor bears its advertising cost alone since the distributor is not receiving any assistance from the manufacturer but this will definitely have an influence on the price availed to the retailer. Moreover this should be done with the intention of optimization of profit among the channel members and the entire system. The price is equally coordinated by the three members to avoid marginalization of consumers. Two models will be developed: a coordinated cooperative model and uncooperative advertising model. A comparison of the two models shows that in a cooperative advertising and pricing system (a) the participation rate of the manufacturer, distributor and retailer in advertising effort are higher compared to when there is no involvement of the distributor and manufacturer. (b) The final consumer will buy from the retailer at a lower price due to the participation of the three channel members in advertising effort (c) Optimum pricing will be achieved by the three channel members.

We will also determine the impact of the distributor in a supply chain by comparison of a two-channel relationship model without the distributor i.e manufacturer-retailer relationship and a three-channel relationship model involving the distributor i.e manufacturer-distributor-retailer relationship. Where the distributor is directly involved in advertising effort and also in availing subsidy to the retailer.

Cooperative advertising is an arrangement in which the manufacturer participate in payment of the advertising fee done by the retailer. It is a well - coordinated effort made by each member of the supply chain to ensure that the product gains large market share in terms of sales. Ezimadu (2019) defined cooperative advertising as an arrangement in which the manufacturer contributes a certain percentage of the advertising expenditure incurred in the course of advertising. Ezimadu (2019) opined that cooperative advertising is usually employed by the manufacturer as a motivational strategy toward the retailer in a supply chain. Xie and Wei (2009) defined cooperative advertising as a practice in which a manufacturer pays the retailer a portion of the local cost of advertising in order to induce sale.

Statement Of The Problem

Several literature and model on cooperative advertising had considered the traditional manufacturer-retailer model which is a two-channel model but Ezimadu (2016) introduced a distributor into a two-channel relationship to form a three-channel relationship. Subsequently, Ezimadu (2019) considered the participatory involvement of the distributor in subsidizing the retailer's effort. Even at that, none of the literature had simultaneously considered the direct involvement of the distributor in the advertising effort and indirect involvement by availing subsidy to the retailer for advertisement. There is rarely any literature on the impact of the distributor in a supply chain. This research seeks to utilize the foundation built by Ezimadu (2016) and (2019) to extend the works of Xie and Wei (2009) on coordinating cooperative advertising and pricing from a manufacturer-retailer relationship to manufacturer-distributor-retailer relationship which is a three channel relationship where the distributor is simultaneously involved in direct and indirect advertising effort. The distributor is a powerful factor in the supply channel, hence we shall look at the impact of the distributor in the coordinated cooperative advertisement and pricing.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the work are as follows.

- i. Design a model for the profitability of the Retailer, Distributor and Manufacturer which are the three channel member in a supply chain.
- ii. Derive a closed-form equilibrium pay-off functions for the channel members and entire channel.
- iii. Determine the impact of the distributor in a coordinated three channel relationship.
- iv. Determine and compare the advertising effort and channel members price function for the subsidized and unsubsidised channel.

Model Development

This research will focus on a manufacturer-distributor-retailer channel in a monopolistic setting the advertising effort, participation rate and pricing are well coordinated among the channel members to ensure maximum payoff for the members of the channel. The distributor is directly involved in advertisement while the retailer is directly involved in local advertisement. Both the manufacture and the distributor are involved in subsidising the advertisement effort of the retailer. The decision variables for the retailer are advertising effort a_R and price, the decision variable for the distributor are advertising effort a_D , price and participation rate in subsidising the retailer's effort while the manufacturer's decision variable are price and participation rate in subsidising the advertisement effort.

Let P_R, P_D, P_M be the price of the retailer, distributor and manufacturer respectively.

P_R : retailer's price

P_D : distributor's price

P_M : manufacturer's price

β_M : manufacturer's participation rate

β_D : distributor's participation rate

a_R : retailer advertising effort

a_D : distributor advertising effort

$D(P_R, a_R, a_D)$

The retail demand function depends on the retail price, the distributor advertising effort and the retailer's local advertising effort.

$$D(P_R, a_R, a_D) = g(P_R) h \tag{4.1}$$

where $g(P_R)$ is the impact of the retail price on demand,

$h(a_R, a_D)$ is the impact of the various advertising level. This idea of modelling demand using multiplicative effect of price and advertising can be found in (Kuehn, 1962; Thompson and Teng 1984; Yue et al. 2006; Xie and Wei, 2009; Ezimadu, 2019). We shall adopt the assumption that $g(P_R)$ is linearly decreasing with respect to with price P_R as seen in literatures (i.e Jeuland and Shugan, 1988, Weng, 1995).

Hence

$$g(P_R) = 1 - \gamma P_R \tag{4.2}$$

Where γ is a positive constant. We normalize $g(P_R)$ to 1 for the sake of simplification

$$g(P_R) \leq 1$$

(Jorgensen et al., 2000; Huang et al., 2002) stated that the advertising effort of each members of the channel has great influence on sale and this effort shall be separately assessed.

Hence,

$$h(a_R, a_D) = h_R \sqrt{a_R} + h_D \sqrt{a_D} \tag{4.3}$$

where h_R, h_D are positive constants showing impact of retailer advertisement expenditure and distributor's advertisement expenditure in generating sales. Simeon and Arndt (1980) noted that the shape of advertising demand function is diminishing in nature.

From (4.1), (4.2) and (4.3)

$$D(P_R, a_R, a_D) = (1 - \gamma P_R)(h_R \sqrt{a_R} + h_D \sqrt{a_D}) \quad (4.4)$$

According to Ezimadu (2019), the profit of the retailer is given by

$$\pi_R = (P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)(h_R \sqrt{a_R} + h_D \sqrt{a_D}) - a_R + \beta_M a_R + \beta_D a_R \quad (4.5)$$

From (4.5), it can be seen that the profit of the retailer is model on a game setting that there is cooperation in advertising effort and pricing when the retailer is directly involved in direct advertising expense and the retailer also receives subsidy from the manufacturer and distributor to support its advertising effort.

Ezimadu (2019) noted that the profit of the distributor is

$$\pi_D = (P_D - P_M)(1 - \gamma P_R)(h_R \sqrt{a_R} + h_D \sqrt{a_D}) - \beta_D a_R - a_D \quad (4.6)$$

From (4.6), the profit of the distributor is model on a setting that there is coordination in advertising and pricing when the distributor is directly involved in direct advertising effort and also provides subsidy in support of the retailers advertising effort.

According to Ezimadu (2019), the profit of the manufacturer is

$$\pi_M = P_M(1 - \gamma P_R)(h_R \sqrt{a_R} + h_D \sqrt{a_D}) - \beta_M a_R \quad (4.7)$$

From (4.7), The profit of the manufacturer is model on a setting that there is coordination between advertising and pricing when the manufacturer is not directly involved in advertising effort but his participatory involvement is through subsidy provision to the retailers advertising effort.

From (4.5), (4.6) and (4.7), the profit of the entire system is

$$\pi_{R+D+M} = P_R(1 - \gamma P_R)(h_R \sqrt{a_R} + h_D \sqrt{a_D}) - a_R - a_D \quad (4.8)$$

Decision Model: Retailer's Optimal Problem

We shall model the decision process as a leader -follower relationship model where the manufacturer is the stackelberg leader and the distributor and the retailer are the followers. We will use Backward induction to solve this Stackelberg equilibrium. Given that the decision variable of manufacture which are its price P_M and its participation rate β_M and that of the distributor which is P_D , advertising effort a_D and participate rate β_D , the retailer will seek to maximize profit.

$$\text{Max } \pi_R = (P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)(h_R \sqrt{a_R} + h_D \sqrt{a_D}) - a_R + \beta_M a_R + \beta_D a_R \quad (4.9)$$

$$\text{s.t } 0 < P_R < 1/\gamma, \quad a_R > 0$$

The distributor also seek to maximize profit

$$\text{Max } \pi_D = (P_D - P_M)(1 - \gamma P_R)(h_R \sqrt{a_R} + h_D \sqrt{a_D}) - \beta_D a_R - a_D \quad (4.10)$$

$$s. t \ P_D \geq 0, a_D > 0$$

The manufacturer decision will be to maximize profit

$$Max \ \pi_M = P_M(1 - \gamma P_R)(h_R\sqrt{a_R} + h_D\sqrt{a_D}) - \beta_M a_R \tag{4.11}$$

$$s. t \ 0 \leq \beta_M \leq 1, P_M \geq 0$$

The optimal value of the retail advertising effort, distributor’s advertising effort, retail price can be obtained by the solving below

$$\frac{\partial \pi_R}{\partial a_R} = 0$$

Maximizing (4.9) with to respect to a_R , then solving we have

$$\frac{\partial \pi_R}{\partial a_R} = 0$$

From (4.9) we have

$$Max \ \pi_R = (P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)(h_R\sqrt{a_R} + h_D\sqrt{a_D}) - a_R + \beta_M a_R + \beta_D a_R$$

$$Max \ \pi_R = (P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)(h_R\sqrt{a_R} + (P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R) h_D\sqrt{a_D}) - a_R(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)$$

$$s. t \ 0 < P_R < 1/\gamma, \quad a_R > 0$$

Maximizing w.r.t a_R we have that

$$\frac{\partial \pi_R}{\partial a_R} = (P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)h_R \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{a_R} - 1 + \beta_M + \beta_D = 0$$

$$(P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)h_R \frac{1}{2\sqrt{a_R}} + 0 - (1 + \beta_M + \beta_D) = 0 \text{ Type equation here.}$$

$$(P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)h_R \frac{1}{2\sqrt{a_R}} = 1 - \beta_M - \beta_D$$

$$2a_R^{\frac{1}{2}}(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D) = (P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)h_R$$

$$a_R^{\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{(P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)h_R}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)}$$

$$a_R = \left[\frac{(P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)h_R}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} \right]^2 \quad (4.12)$$

From (4.9) we have

$$\text{Max } \pi_R = (P_R - \gamma P_R^2 - P_D + \gamma P_D P_R)(h_R \sqrt{a_R} + h_D \sqrt{a_D}) - a_R(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)$$

$$\text{s.t } 0 < P_R < 1/\gamma, \quad a_R > 0$$

Maximizing w.r.t P_R we have that

$$\frac{\partial \pi_R}{\partial P_R} = (1 - 2\gamma P_R + \gamma P_D)((h_R \sqrt{a_R} + h_D \sqrt{a_D})) - 0 = 0$$

$$(1 - 2\gamma P_R + \gamma P_D)((h_R \sqrt{a_R} + h_D \sqrt{a_D})) = 0$$

$$1 - 2\gamma P_R + \gamma P_D = 0$$

$$-2\gamma P_R = -1 - \gamma P_D$$

$$P_R = \frac{1 + \gamma P_D}{2\gamma} \quad (4.13)$$

Using (4.12) and (4.13) in (4.10) we have

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Max } \pi_D = & (P_D - P_M) \left(1 - \gamma \frac{1 + \gamma P_D}{2\gamma} \right) \left(h_R \left(\frac{h_R (P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)h_R}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} \right)^2 + h_D \sqrt{a_D} \right) \\ & - \beta_D \left[\frac{(P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)h_R}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} \right]^2 - a_D \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{s.t } P_D > 0, \quad a_D > 0$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= (P_D - P_M) \left[1 - \frac{1 + \gamma P_D}{2} \right] \left(\frac{h_R^2 (P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} - \frac{h_R^2 P_D (1 - \gamma P_R)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} + h_D \sqrt{a_D} \right) - \\
 &\quad - \beta_D \left[\frac{(P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R) h_R}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} \right]^2 - a_D
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.14}$$

s.t $P_D > 0, a_D > 0$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= (P_D - P_M) \left[1 - \frac{1 + \gamma P_D}{2} \right] \left(\frac{h_R^2 (P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} - \frac{h_R^2 P_D (1 - \gamma P_R)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} + h_D \sqrt{a_D} \right) - \\
 &\quad - \beta_D \left[\frac{(P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R) h_R}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} \right]^2 - a_D \\
 &= (P_D - P_M) \left[1 - \frac{1}{2} - \frac{\gamma P_D}{2} \right] \left(\frac{h_R^2 (P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} - \frac{h_R^2 P_D (1 - \gamma P_R)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} \right) - \beta_D \left[\frac{(P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R) h_R}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} \right]^2 - P_D
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.14}$$

S.t $P_D > 0, a_D > 0$

Maximizing w.r.t a_D , we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\partial \pi_D}{\partial a_D} &= (P_D - P_M) \left[1 - \frac{1}{2} - \frac{\gamma P_D}{2} \right] \cdot \frac{1}{2} h_D a_D^{-\frac{1}{2}} - 1 = 0 \\
 \Rightarrow \frac{(P_D - P_M) \left[1 - \frac{1}{2} - \frac{\gamma P_D}{2} \right] h_D}{2 a_D^{\frac{1}{2}}} &= 1 \\
 \Rightarrow a_D^{\frac{1}{2}} &= \frac{(P_D - P_M) \left[1 - \frac{1}{2} - \frac{\gamma P_D}{2} \right] h_D}{2}
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.15}$$

$$\Rightarrow a_D = \left[\frac{(P_D - P_M) [1 - \gamma P_D] h_D}{4} \right]^2 \tag{4.16}$$

Maximizing (4.14) w.r.t P_D , we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \pi_D}{\partial P_D} &= 1 \cdot \left[1 - \frac{1}{2} - \frac{\gamma P_D}{2} \right] \left(\frac{h_R^2(P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} - \frac{h_R^2 P_D(1 - \gamma P_R)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} + h_D \sqrt{a_D} \right) + \\ & (P_D - P_M) \left(-\frac{\gamma}{2} \right) \left[\left(\frac{h_R^2(P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} - \frac{h_R^2 P_D(1 - \gamma P_R)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} \right) + h_D \sqrt{a_D} + (P_D - P_M) \left[1 - \frac{1}{2} - \frac{\gamma P_D}{2} \right] \cdot \left[\frac{h_R^2(1 - \gamma P_R)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} \right] - 2\beta_D \left(\frac{h_R^2(P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} \right) \right] = 0 \\ & \Rightarrow \left[\frac{1}{2} - \frac{\gamma P_D}{2} \right] \left(\frac{h_R^2(P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} - \frac{h_R^2 P_D(1 - \gamma P_R)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} + \right) h_D \sqrt{a_D} \cdot \left(\frac{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} - \right) + \\ & (P_D - P_M) \left(-\frac{\gamma}{2} \right) \left(\frac{h_R^2(P_R)(1 - \gamma P_R)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} - \frac{h_R^2 P_R(1 - \gamma P_R)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} \right) + h_D \sqrt{a_D} \cdot \left(\frac{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} \right) + (P_D - P_M) \left[\frac{1}{2} - \frac{\gamma P_D}{2} \right] \cdot \left[\frac{h_R^2(1 - \gamma P_R)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} \right] - 2\beta_D \left(\frac{h_R(P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_D)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} \right) \\ & = 0 \\ & \Rightarrow \left[\frac{1}{2} - \frac{\gamma P_D}{2} \right] \cdot \left[\frac{h_R^2 P_R(1 - \gamma P_R) - h_R^2 P_D(1 - \gamma P_R) + h_D \sqrt{a_D} \cdot (2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} \right. \\ & \left. + h_D \sqrt{a_D} \cdot \frac{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} \right] \\ & + (P_D - P_M) \left(-\frac{\gamma}{2} \right) \cdot \frac{(h_R^2 P_R(1 - \gamma P_R) - h_R^2 P_D(1 - \gamma P_R) + h_D \sqrt{a_D} \cdot (2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} \quad (P_D \\ & - P_M) \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{\gamma P_D}{2} \right) \left(-\frac{h_R^2 P_R(1 - \gamma P_R)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} \right) \cdot 2\beta_D \left[\frac{h_R(P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} \right] = 0 \\ & \frac{1}{2(2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D))} \left((1 - \gamma P_D)(h_R^2 P_D(1 - \gamma P_R) - (h_R^2 P_D(1 - \gamma P_D) + h_D \sqrt{a_D} \cdot 2(2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D))) \right) \\ & + \\ & (P_D - P_M)(-\gamma)(h_R^2(1 - \gamma P_R) - \gamma(1 - \gamma P_R) + h_D \sqrt{a_D} \cdot 2(2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)) + \\ & (P_D - P_M)(1 - \gamma P_D)(h_D^2)(1 - \gamma P_R) - 2\beta_D \cdot 2(h_R(P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R) = 0 \\ & (-P_M)\gamma^2 h_R^2 P_R^2 + 2P_D P_M P_R \gamma^2 h_R^2 + 2P_R^2 P_D \gamma^2 h_R^2 - 3P_R P_D^2 P_D \gamma^2 h_R^2 - \gamma h_R^2 P_R^2 \\ & - 3P_M^2 P_D \gamma^2 h_R^2 + 4\sqrt{a_D} \beta_M P_D h_D \gamma + 4\sqrt{a_D} \beta_M P_D h_D \gamma \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & -2\sqrt{a_D}\beta_M\beta_D P_D h_D \gamma - 2\sqrt{a_D}\beta_D P_M h_D \gamma - 4\beta_D P_D h_R - 4\beta_D P_R h_R - 2P_D h_R - \\
 & 2\sqrt{a_D}\beta_M h_D - 2\sqrt{a_D}\beta_D h_D + 2\sqrt{a_D}\beta_D \\
 & =0
 \end{aligned}$$

$$3\gamma p_D^2 h_R^2 - 3P_R \gamma p_D^2 h_R^2 + 2P_D P_M P_R \gamma^2 h_R^2 +$$

2

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P_D P_R^2 \gamma^2 h_R^2 - 4\beta_D h_R P_D P_R \gamma - 2P_D h_R - 4\sqrt{a_D} P_D h_D \gamma + 4\beta_D P_D h_R - 2P_D h_R^2 - \\
 & 2\sqrt{a_D}\beta_M h_D P_M \gamma - 2\sqrt{a_D}\beta_D h_D P_M \gamma +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$2\sqrt{a_D}\beta_D h_D + 2\sqrt{a_D}\beta_D - P_D P_M \gamma^2 h_R^2 - \gamma P_R^2 h_R^2 + 4\beta_D h_R P_R^2 = 0$$

$$((-3) P_R \gamma^2 h_R^2 - 3\gamma h_R^2) p_D^2 +$$

$$(2P_M P_R \gamma^2 h_R^2) + 2\gamma^2 h_R^2 P_R^2 - 4\beta_D h_R P_R \gamma - 2P_M \gamma h_R +$$

$$4\sqrt{a_D}\beta_D h_D \gamma - 4\sqrt{a_D} h_D \gamma + 4\beta_D h_R - 2h_R^2$$

$$2\sqrt{a_D} h_D P_M \gamma - 2\sqrt{a_D}\beta_D h_D + 2\sqrt{a_D} h_D - P_M \gamma^2 h_R^2 P_R^2 - \gamma h_R^2 P_R^2 + 4\beta_D \gamma P_R h_R$$

Using quadratic formula

$$P_D = \frac{-b \pm \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a} \tag{4.17}$$

Where

$$a = (-3)P_R \gamma^2 h_R^2 + 3\gamma h_R^2$$

$$b = 2$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P_M P_R \gamma^2 h_R^2 + 2\gamma^2 h_R^2 P_R^2 - 4\beta_D P_R h_R \gamma - 2P_M \gamma h_R^2 + 4\sqrt{a_D \beta_M} h_D \gamma + 4\sqrt{a_D \beta_D} h_D \gamma - \\
 & 4\sqrt{a_D} h_D \gamma
 \end{aligned}$$

C=-

2

$$\sqrt{a_D}\beta_M h_D P_M \gamma - 2\sqrt{a_D}\beta_D h_D P_M \gamma + P_M h_R^2 + P_M h_R^2 + 2\sqrt{a_D}h_D - 4\beta_D h_R P_R - 2\sqrt{a_D}\beta_M h_D - 2\sqrt{a_D}\beta_D h_D + 2\sqrt{a_D}h_D - P_M h_R^2 \gamma^2 P_R^2 - \gamma h_R^2 P_R^2 + 4\beta_D h_R \gamma P_R^2$$

$$\pi_D = (P_D - P_M) \left(\frac{1 - \gamma P_D}{2} \right) \left[\frac{h_R^2 (P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} + h_D \sqrt{a_D} \right] - \left[\frac{h_R^2 (P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} \right]^2 - \alpha_D$$

Maximizing (4.13) w.r.t β_D , we have

$$\frac{\partial \pi_D}{\partial \beta_D} =$$

$$(P_D - P_M) \left(\frac{1 - \gamma P_D}{2} \right) \left[\frac{h_R^2 (P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)}{2} \cdot (1)(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)^{-2} \cdot (-1) \right] -$$

$$\beta_D \left[\frac{h_R^2 (P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} \right]^2 \cdot (-2)(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)^{-3} \cdot (-1) - \left[\frac{h_R^2 (P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} \right]^2$$

$$\Rightarrow (P_D - P_M) \left(\frac{1 - \gamma P_D}{2} \right) \left[\frac{h_R^2 (P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} \right] - \beta_D \left[\frac{h_R^2 (P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} \right]^2 \cdot \frac{2}{(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} +$$

$$\left[\frac{h_R^2 (P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} \right]^2 = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow (P_D - P_M) \left(\frac{1 - \gamma P_D}{2} \right) \left[\left[\frac{h_R^2 (P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} \right] + \left[\frac{h_R^2 (P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} \right]^2 \right. \\ \left. = \beta_D \left[\frac{h_R^2 (P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} \right]^2 \cdot \frac{2}{(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} \right]$$

$$\Rightarrow (P_D - P_M) \left(\frac{1 - \gamma P_D}{2} \right) \left[h_R^2 (P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R) + (h_R^2 (P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R))^2 \right] \\ = \beta_D \left[\frac{h_R^2 (P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} \right]^2$$

$$\Rightarrow (P_D - P_M) \left(\frac{1 - \gamma P_D}{2} \right) + \frac{2h_R^2(P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)}{2} = \beta_D \left[\frac{h_R^2(P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} \right]$$

$$\Rightarrow (1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)[(P_D - P_M)](1 - \gamma P_D) + 2h_R^2(P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R) =$$

$$\beta_D h_R^2(P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)$$

$$\Rightarrow (1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)[(P_D - P_M) + 2h_R^2(P_R - P_D)] = \beta_D h_R^2(P_R - P_D)$$

$$\Rightarrow (1 - \beta_M)[P_D - P_M + 2h_R^2(P_R - P_D)] =$$

$$\beta_D [P_D - P_M + 2h_R^2(P_R - P_D)] = \beta_D h_R^2(P_R - P_D)$$

$$\Rightarrow \beta_D h_R^2(P_R - P_D) +$$

$$\beta_D [P_D - P_M + 2h_R^2(P_R - P_D)] = (1 - \beta_M)[P_D - P_M + 2h_R^2(P_R - P_D)]$$

$$\Rightarrow \beta_D [h_R^2(P_R - P_D) + (P_D - P_M) + 2h_R^2(P_R - P_D)] = (1 - \beta_M) [P_D - P_M + 2h_R^2(P_R - P_D)]$$

$$\Rightarrow \beta_D = \frac{(1 - \beta_M)[P_D - P_M + 2h_R^2(P_R - P_D)]}{h_R^2(P_R - P_D) + (P_D - P_M) + 2h_R^2(P_R - P_D)} \tag{4.18}$$

$$\text{Max } \pi_M = P_M(1 - \gamma P_R)(h_R\sqrt{a_R} + h_D\sqrt{a_D}) - \beta_M a_R$$

Using (4.11) and (4.16) in (4.10) , we have

$$\begin{aligned} &\Rightarrow P_M(1 - \gamma P_R)h_R\sqrt{\left[\frac{(P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)h_R}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)}\right]^2} + h_D\sqrt{\left[\frac{(P_D - P_M)[1 - \gamma P_D]h_D}{4}\right]^2} - \\ &\beta_M \left[\frac{(P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)h_R}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)}\right]^2 \\ &\Rightarrow P_M(1 - \gamma P_R) \left[\frac{h_R^2(P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)}\right] + \left[\frac{(P_D - P_M)[1 - \gamma P_D]h_D^2}{4}\right] - \beta_M \left[\frac{h_R(P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)}\right]^2 \end{aligned} \tag{4.19}$$

Maximizing w.r.t P_M , we have

$$\frac{\partial \pi_M}{\partial P_M} = \left[\frac{(1 - \gamma P_R)(h_R^2(P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R))}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} \right] - \left[\frac{2h_D(P_D - P_M)[1 - \gamma P_D]}{4} \right] = 0$$

Let h_R and h_D assume the values 0.3 and 0.2 respectively

$$\begin{aligned} &\Rightarrow \left[\frac{(1 - \gamma P_R)^2(0.3)^2(P_R - P_D)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} \right] - \left[\frac{2(0.2)^2(P_D - P_M)[1 - \gamma P_D]}{4} \right] = 0 \\ &\Rightarrow \left[\frac{(1 - \gamma P_R)^2(0.3)^2(P_R - P_D)}{2(1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} \right] = \left[\frac{2(0.2)^2(P_D - P_M)[1 - \gamma P_D]}{4} \right] \\ &\Rightarrow \left[\frac{4(1 - \gamma P_R)^2(0.3)^2(P_R - P_D)}{2 \cdot 2(0.2)^2(P_D - P_M)[1 - \gamma P_D](1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} \right] \\ &\Rightarrow \left[\frac{4(1 - \gamma P_R)^2(3)^2(10)(P_R - P_D)}{4(2)^2(10)(P_D - P_M)[1 - \gamma P_D](1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} \right] \\ &\Rightarrow P_M = \frac{9(1 - \gamma P_R)^2(P_R - P_D)}{4(P_D)[1 - \gamma P_D](1 - \beta_M - \beta_D)} \end{aligned} \tag{4.20}$$

From (4.13), it can be seen clearly that the retailer will set its price based on the price received from the distributor but will neither depend on the distributions advertisement expenditure nor its subsidy availment to the retailer. From (4.17), it can be seen that the distributor's price (P_D) is linearly increasing function of the manufacturer's price (P_M) but has no connection with the manufacturer's participation rate (β_M). From (4.20), it can be seen that the manufacturer's price (P_M) will depend on its participation rate (β) in the advertisement effort.

UNCOORDINATED SCENARIO

In an uncoordinated scenario, the manufacturer and the distributor are neither involved in advertising effort nor in subsidizing the retail advertising effort. Only the retailer is fully involved in advertising the manufacturer goods i.e $\beta_M = 0$ and $\beta_D = 0$; $h_D\sqrt{a_D} = 0$

COORDINATED SCENARIO

In a coordinated scenario, since the manufacturer and the distributor are involved in provision of subsidy to the retail advertising effort, while the distributor and the retailer are involved in advertisement at various levels.

$$\beta_M > 0 \text{ and } \beta_D > 0; h_D\sqrt{a_D} \text{ and } h_R\sqrt{a_R}$$

Impact Of The Distributor In A Coordinated Channel Relationship

$$\pi_R = (P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)(h_R\sqrt{a_R} + h_D\sqrt{a_D}) - a_R + \beta_M a_R + \beta_D a_R$$

$$\pi_D = (P_D - P_M)(1 - \gamma P_R)(h_R\sqrt{a_R} + h_D\sqrt{a_D}) - \beta_D a_R - a_D$$

$$\pi_M = P_M(1 - \gamma P_R)(h_R\sqrt{a_R} + h_D\sqrt{a_D}) - \beta_M a_R$$

To understand the impact of the distributor in a supply chain, we consider (4.4),(4.5) & (4.6) which is a scenario where the distributor is directly involved in advertising and indirectly at participatory level in a three member relationship. We shall also consider a two channel: scenario where only the retailer is involved in local advertisement effort and the manufacturer is indirectly involved through subsidy availment to the retailer as represented in the model below

$$\pi_M = P_M(1 - \gamma P_R)(h_R\sqrt{a_R}) - \beta_M a_R \quad (4.21)$$

$$\pi_R = (P_M - P_R)(1 - \gamma P_R)(h_R\sqrt{a_R}) - a_R + \beta_M a_R \quad (4.22)$$

$h_R\sqrt{a_R}$ - is the retailer advertising effort

We have model these two channel member relationship (manufacturer-retailer) using the same parameters with the three member relationship for ease of comparison

COMPARISON

$$\pi_R = (P_R - P_D)(1 - \gamma P_R)(h_R\sqrt{a_R} + h_D\sqrt{a_D}) - a_R + \beta_M a_R + \beta_D a_R \quad (4.22 b)$$

$$\pi_R = (P_M - P_R)(1 - \gamma P_R)(h_R\sqrt{a_R}) - a_R + \beta_M a_R$$

To understand the impact of the distributor in determining player's profit, we assume that the price difference (margin) between the manufacturer and the retailer is equal to the price difference (margin) between the retailer and the distributor.

A comparison of (4.22) and (4.22b); which is a comparison of a player model where only the manufacturer and the retailer are involved in a channel relationship with only the retailer directly involved in advertising effort while the manufacturer subsidizes the retailer's effort to a game model where the distributor is incorporated to the scenario to simultaneously advertise directly and to be involved in provision of subsidy to the retailer's advertising effort gives

$$\pi_R = (1 - \gamma P_R) h_D \sqrt{a_D} + \beta_D a_R \quad (4.23)$$

(4.23) shows that the involvement of the distributor in a supply chain will clearly impact the profit of the retailer. The retailer's profit will be greatly influence by the participatory effort of the distributor in subsidy availment and the positive multiplicative effect of the distributor's direct advertising effort. The greater the participatory effort of the distributor, the greater the profitability of the retailer but as the distributor withdraws its participatory effort, the profit of the retailer will decrease

$$\pi_M = P_M(1 - \gamma P_R)(h_R \sqrt{a_R} + h_D \sqrt{a_D}) - \beta_M a_R$$

$$\pi_M = P_M(1 - \gamma P_R)(h_R \sqrt{a_R}) - \beta_M a_R$$

Comparison of (4.7) and (38) gives

$$\pi_{M=(1-\gamma P_R) h_D \sqrt{a_D}} \quad (4.24)$$

It can clearly be seen from (4.24) that the advertising effort of the distributor at its level has a direct positive impact on sales, this translates to greater profit for the manufacturer. That is the greater the advertising effort of the distributor, the greater the profit of the manufacturer. This goes to show that every wise manufacturer needs the active involvement of the role of a distributor to command greater profit. This important link between the manufacturer and the retailer called the distributor is now being engaged both offline and online as seen by giant companies globally

From (4.23) and (4.24) it is very obvious that both the advertising effort of the distributor and its direct involvement in advertising effort has major positive impact on the channel member payoff in a supply chain. This singular reason makes the distributor a force to be reckon with in a supply chain. Hence a three channel relationship with the involvement of the distributor will command greater channel wise profit for the members and entire system than a two member channel relationship where only the manufacturer and retailer is involved.

ANALYSIS OF PLAYER'S PERFORMANCE USING GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION

Figure 1: The Effect of distributors subsidy Rate on the players' payoff

From figure 1, It can be seen that the margin of the manufacturer is larger than that of the distributor and retailer, this is because the manufacturer is stackelberg leader hence enjoys the first mover advantage, while the distributor is the first follower and the retailer is the second follower. As the distributor gets fully involved in provision of subsidy, its pay-off reduces and diminish quickly as a result of its simultaneous involvement in direct advertising and subsidy provision while the pay-off of the manufacturer and retailer increases rapidly until it becomes unbounded. The distributor must adopt an optimal strategy in other to remain in business and not be thrown out.

Figure 2: The Effect of Manufacturer subsidy Rate on the players' payoff

From figure 2 , it can be seen that as the participation rate of the manufacturer increase its pay-off will continue to decrease and the pay-off of the retailer and the distributor will continue to increase. Even though the manufacturer is not involved in direct advertising, the manufacturer must adopt the best strategy to remain profitably in business.

Figure 3: The Effect of advertising effort without the support or participation from distributor and Manufacturer on the players' payoff

Form figure 3, only the retailer is involved in advertising effort without any support or participation from the distributor and manufacturer. It can be seen that the retailer enjoys marginal increase for a while before it starts to diminish as it advertising effort increases. The manufacture and distributor enjoys unbounded pay-off form the advertising effort of the retailer which they both have no participation. The retailer must adopt optimal strategy in terms of its advertising effort since that it is its decision variable

Figure 4: The Effect of advertising effort with the support or participation from distributor and Manufacturer on the players' payoff

Figure 4 shows a scenario where both the distributor and retailer is involved in direct advertising effort while the distributor and the manufacture provides subsidy support to the retail advertising effort. It can be seen that all player enjoys marginal increase in their pay but as the advertising effort and subsidy availment increases the distributor is overwhelmed and overburden as a result of its simultaneous involvement in both direct and indirect advertising .The distributor begins to experience sharp fall in its pay-off and begins to struggle to survive if optimal strategy is not adopted. Hence the distributor must adopt optimal strategy in terms of its price, advertising effort and subsidy rate. The retailer continues to enjoy maximum pay-off since its advertising effort is subsidized by both the manufacture and the distributor. All members of the channel must ensure that optimal strategy is adopted to avoid being put out of business.

ENTIRE SYSTEM PAY-OFF AND ADVERTISING EFFORT FOR TWO CHANNEL RELATIONSHIP AND A THREE CHANNEL RELATIONSHIP

Figure 5: The system payoff and Advertising effort for two and three channel

It can be seen clearly that in a two member relationship involving the retailer and the manufacturer, the profit of the entire system is much lower because only the retailer is involved in the advertising effort hence may not be able to reach wider range of customers while the manufacturer provides subsidy. This direct and indirect effort of the retailer and the manufacturer will definitely take a chunk of their profit .But when the distributor is in-cooperated into the relationship, the advertising effort increases as a result of the simultaneous involvement of the distributor in direct advertising effort and its effort in pulling resource towards the retailer’s advertising effort. This will translate into greater profit for the entire system since the burden of advertising is now been equally bore by the distributor who is an integral part of the entire system

FINDINGS

The major findings for this research are as follows:

- i. The in-cooperation of the distributor as a member of the supply chain to both assist in directly advertisement and indirectly participate in subsidy availment yields better channel wise profit for the entire system.
- ii. Optimum strategy must be adopted by the distributor in terms of its pricing, subsidy rate and advertising to ensure that it remains profitable in business and not pushed out as a result of its over –involvement in advertising activities.
- iii. Over-subsidization of the retailer’s advertising effort by both the manufacturer and the distributor will make the retailers profit unbounded and excessive.

CONCLUSION

In this dissertation, we used the game -theory to model a cooperative advertising and pricing policy in a manufacturer-Distributor -Retailer relationship. The multiplicative effect of the price and advertising was used to model the demand function. Two scenarios were considered: coordinated advertising and pricing among the three member and an uncoordinated advertising and pricing scenario. The players profit for each scenario shows that a coordinated scenario yields greater profit for the channel members compared to the uncoordinated scenario .we probed further on the impact of the distributor in a the supply chain by

considering and comparing a Manufacturer –retailer two member relationship and Manufacturer-Distributor -Retailer three member relationship when the distributor is incorporated to the supply chain as a direct advertiser of the manufacturer’s product and also indirectly involved in provision of subsidy to the retailer advertising effort . This paper utilized the foundation built by Ezimadu (2006) to extend the works of xie and Wie (2009) . we obtained the model for the player’s profit and advertising strategies both for the subsidised scenario and the unsubsidised scenario and observed that the subsidised scenario is a better strategy for yielding better profit for the entire system.The graphical analysis of the player’s profit and entire system profit establishes the fact that the distributor is a major force in the supply chain

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the finding, the following recommendations were made:

1. Manufacturers and producers must fully recognize the importance of the distributor and fully utilize them as an integral part of the supply chain
2. Industries must adopt optimum advertising strategy among the distributor and retailer in other not to over burden the retailer or over subsidized its advertising effort
3. Lectures and researchers can also utilize this work as a foundation for understanding the role of a distributor in a supply chain when the distributor is simultaneously involved in direct and indirect advertising

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